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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHOROIDAL VASCULARITY INDEX IN PRIMARY OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA, NORMAL-TENSION GLAUCOMA AND HEALTHY INDIVIDUALS

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Purpose: This cross-sectional prospective study aimed to assess and compare peripapillary choroidal vascularity index (CVI) parameters in patients with primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG), normal-tension glaucoma (NTG), and healthy controls.

Methods: A total of 120 eyes from 120 participants were included, comprising (i) 40 eyes of 40 patients with POAG, (ii) 40 eyes of 40 patients with NTG, and (iii) 40 eyes of healthy controls. Peripapillary enhanced depth imaging optical coherence tomography images were processed using standard protocols with ImageJ software for binarization. CVI values were analyzed across all sectors of the peripapillary region.

Results: The study revealed a significantly lower peripapillary CVI in the POAG group (62.1 ± 2.45) compared to the NTG group (65.3 ± 3.02) and healthy controls (68.2 ± 2.56) ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, NTG patients exhibited significantly lower CVI values than healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). The detailed sectoral analysis demonstrated significantly lower peripapillary CVI values in the temporal, nasal, supratemporal, superonasal, inferotemporal, and inferonasal sectors of the POAG group compared to both the NTG group and controls ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, NTG patients exhibited lower peripapillary CVI in all sectors than healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). Global peripapillary choroidal thickness was significantly thinner in the POAG group ($135.8 \pm 38.42 \mu\text{m}$) than in the NTG ($157.4 \pm 35.29 \mu\text{m}$) and control groups ($160.2 \pm 37.09 \mu\text{m}$) ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: This study highlights a significant reduction in peripapillary CVI in POAG and NTG patients, with the most pronounced decrease observed in the POAG group. The findings suggest that CVI may be valuable for indicating vascular dysfunction in POAG and NTG. Further research is needed to validate these results and explore the clinical implications of CVI in glaucomatous optic neuropathy.